

Additive Manufacturing and Optimization of MoNiCr Alloy Production for Modern Energy Applications

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Abstract: One of the concepts under consideration for Generation IV nuclear reactors is a molten salt coolant system. The critical point is the material used for the primary and secondary circuit components of the power source. The material is subjected to extreme chemical and thermal stresses. Due to the unavailability of these materials, such as the Russian alloy HN80M, the French alloys EM-721 and EM-722 and the Chinese alloy GH3535, a nickel alloy called MoNiCr has been developed in the Czech Republic. In the present paper, the production of MoNiCr alloy is discussed from conventional casting technology, through forming, powder atomization, additive manufacturing (AM), to final heat treatment. The final experimental sample was fabricated using Directed-Energy-Deposition (DED) additive manufacturing technology. This advanced fabrication technology was chosen because of the possibilities of designing complex and intricate shapes of component structures applicable in this area of the energy industry, which often cannot be produced by conventional technologies. MoNiCr is a very difficult to form material with a high tendency to form solidification cracks during additive manufacturing. Nevertheless, by using a suitable chemical composition and technological procedure, a test body with almost no defects and suitable mechanical properties was produced by additive manufacturing.

Keywords: nickel alloy MoNiCr; additive manufacturing (AM); directed-energy-deposition (DED); miniature tensile test specimens (MTT); solidification cracking, molten salt reactor (MSR)

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1. Introduction

Present nuclear reactors have consistently been a major source of low carbon energy. Nevertheless, the next generation of reactors is being developed to ensure better efficiency, sustainability and safety. Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) is one of the most promising advanced reactors 4th classified among the Generation IV reactor systems. This reactor system is currently experiencing increased interest from organizations and companies designing also small modular reactors (SMR) [1].

Current research and development are now mainly focused at the level of basic theoretical studies of MSR system, complemented by experimental testing of selected parts of the technology. In the area of materials research, this mainly involves testing the corrosion properties of selected structural materials that could be used for the construction of the MSR. Initial MSR development in the U.S. was focused on a reactor system cooled by fluoride-melt of LiF-BeF₂ composition called FLIBE, for which the nickel alloy Innor-8 was designed at ORNL. The production of this alloy was subsequently taken over by the US metallurgical company Haynes and, under the commercial name Hastelloy N, was used in the 1960s for the design of the MSRE reactor, which was operated from 1965-69. In the

context of the interruption of MSR development, production of Hastelloy N was also discontinued [2]. After 2000, when interest in MSR development was renewed, Hastelloy N was not commercially available, and this led to the testing of other (alternative) commercially available nickel materials that could be used for MSR design. In addition, metallurgical development of new nickel alloys, similar to Hastelloy N, specifically for fluoride-salt cooled MSRs has been undertaken in several cases. Typical representatives of these newly developed alloys are the Czech alloy MONICR, the Russian alloy HN80M, the French EM-721 and EM-722 and the Chinese GH3535 [3]. Of these alloys, only the Chinese alloy GH3535 has been used for the design of the Chinese experimental TMSR (Thorium Molten Salt Reactor) which is currently under construction.

The existing research and development of these alloys and their experimental verification of corrosion resistance and selected mechanical properties has been focused on their potential use as a structural material for MSR and FHR (Fluoride-salt-cooled High-temperature Reactor) systems cooled by fluoride melts, typically the FLIBE melt [2]. After 2020, however, proposals have emerged for MSR-type reactor systems that would operate in the fast neutron spectrum and act as burners (incinerators) for plutonium and other actinides contained in the spent fuel of current nuclear reactors. The coolant (or carrier melt) for their liquid fuel should be a chloride salt melt, typically a binary mixture of NaCl – MgCl₂ or NaCl - CaCl₂. However, no special structural material has yet been developed for this type of chloride MSR, despite the fact that a number of such fast spectrum chloride MSRs are currently in various stages of development [2]. Most of these reactors are also being designed and developed as Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), with significant government support in several countries.

The presented experimental program deals with MoNiCr alloy, namely its metallurgical and additive processing. MoNiCr after proper processing is the single-phase superalloy with f.c.c. solid solution microstructure.

Metallurgical process of MoNiCr alloy should respect specific technological features concerning the atmosphere pressure, batch material purity, the order of melting of individual components, gas homogenization during melting etc. Special attention must be paid to the method of alloying and to the multi-stage deoxidation. Besides deoxidation, sulfur elimination seems to be a critical point during melting. At the same time, it is necessary to optimize the content of accompanying elements to improve deoxidation process and to achieve desired mechanical properties [4].

In terms of forming process, the key steps seem to be the transition of the cast state of the material to the state of a formed recrystallized microstructure with homogenous fine grains [5]. A particular stress condition is, besides the temperature, very important during hot forming. Nickel alloys can accept a significantly higher deformation level if the compressive stress prevails. A forming process involving the compression state of stress increases the probability that the material will reach, without failure, a level of deformation that allows recovery and recrystallization processes [6]. In the case of MoNiCr components forming, recrystallization is a crucial process allowing successful forming. This process is running very slowly or even not running at all, if inappropriate conditions are met. Proper temperature and strain rate range were determined and furthermore the influence of cold deformation on recrystallization progress was determined. It was found that cold deformation before hot forming as well as after hot forming can be successfully implemented into technological chain. Almost fully recrystallized microstructure can be achieved using synergy of both cold and hot deformation [7,8].

Additive manufacturing (AM), also known as 3D printing, has emerged as a promising technology. With AM, the production process is much easier, as the combination of materials in the form of powder and the possibility of changing the material composition here needed are favoured. Recently, the development of AM technologies has also enabled the production of complex geometries of multi-material components with optimized mechanical properties [9–11]. The selection of the method depends on the material system, the desired properties, and the application requirements.

Laser additive manufacturing directed energy deposition (DED) used to prepare final design of samples for testing is a family of additive manufacturing technologies that uses a directed heat source to melt a feedstock material. DED of metals allows additive manufacturing of large-scale metallic components at a much higher deposition rate compared to other AM technologies, such as Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF). In general components manufactured with a DED process are characterized by large part size and relatively low resolution when comparing them with L-PBF [12]. This technology finds the application not just in part fabrication but also in surface cladding and part restoration. Hip implants, blisks, large scale aerospace components, conformal cooling channels, etc. are a few examples of process capability [12]. Fabrication of Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) with superior mechanical properties is perhaps one of the most significant applications of DED [13]. Metal Matrix Composite (MMC) is another budding field of research in DED with the primary focus on feedstock development. Processing of Nickel-based superalloys [14] with relative ease through DED, for applications in high temperature and corrosive environment, has further widened the domain of this technology. The last research focus is developed in the presented manuscript. Additive manufacturing of MoNiCr alloys opens up the possibility of producing parts with significantly more complex shapes compared to conventional processes. The lack of data describing the relations between the chemical composition, the technological procedure and the resulting properties requires research into this method of alloy preparation.

The MoNiCr alloy, however, is prone to solidification cracking—a common issue in nickel-based superalloys—especially during additive manufacturing processes. By adjusting the chemical composition and refining manufacturing techniques, this study seeks to minimize defect formation, enhance material cohesion, and achieve a balance of mechanical properties necessary for high-performance applications. Solidification cracking is a significant metallurgical challenge in nickel-based alloys, often affecting the integrity and performance of components manufactured through processes involving rapid cooling, such as welding and additive manufacturing. Solidification cracking, often observed in nickel-based superalloys, is a significant issue that can occur during solidification processes by additive manufacturing or welding or casting. These cracks typically form along grain boundaries and are characterized by a dendritic structure due to variations in solute concentration during the final stages of solidification. This phenomenon arises because, as the material cools, the last portions of liquid solidify at grain boundaries, where shrinkage and stress localization create weak points [15]. This can lead to deformation shifts at the grain boundaries, resulting in voids and cracks. In materials like austenitic stainless steels and nickel-based superalloys, three primary cracking mechanisms are generally encountered during welding: solidification cracking, ductility dip cracking, and liquation cracking. Solidification cracks occur at the solidification front within the melt pool, specifically in regions where the last liquid solidifies. This location is particularly susceptible to deformation, causing a concentration of stress along the grain boundaries, where cracks are more likely to initiate and propagate. Solidification cracking in nickel alloys presents a challenge due to the high susceptibility of these materials to cracking mechanisms associated with their microstructural and chemical composition. Understanding and controlling solidification behavior is therefore crucial to improving the weldability and structural integrity of nickel-based alloys in high-temperature applications [9,16].

The quality of powder is crucial in additive manufacturing [17], especially in metal 3D printing. Powder properties such as particle shape, size distribution, bulk density, and flowability directly impact the quality of the final part. Spherical particles with a narrow size distribution ensure better flow and even distribution during printing, leading to higher density and improved mechanical properties of the final product. Conversely, irregular particles or a broad size distribution can cause defects such as porosity, lack of fusion or cracks, affecting the accuracy and strength of printed parts. Therefore, careful

selection and quality control of the powder are essential to achieve optimal results in additive manufacturing [18,19].

This research focuses on the development and optimization of the MoNiCr alloy for additive manufacturing applications, primarily aimed at advanced energy systems such as Generation IV molten salt reactors (MSR). MSR technology, with its promise of high efficiency and safety, imposes extreme thermal and chemical demands on structural materials. Due to the unavailability of specialized alloys like Hastelloy N, alternatives like MoNiCr have been developed to withstand the corrosive environments and high temperatures typical of MSR applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Preparation of MoNiCr alloy for Additive Manufacturing

The aim of the research was to develop and verify the nickel alloy MoNiCr for applications in additive manufacturing. The experiment focused on controlling process parameters and material properties to ensure that the resulting material achieved the required chemical composition and purity, which is crucial for its further use in demanding operating conditions.

A key element was the preparation of the alloy using a vacuum induction furnace capable of melting under both vacuum and protective inert gas, preventing contamination of the melt by the surrounding atmosphere and achieving high material purity. The furnace accommodates crucibles with capacities of 50 and 500 kg, with ingots for this work weighing 50 kg. During the alloy development, chemical composition was optimized to improve corrosion resistance and enhance material properties for forming processes. Adjustments were made to the levels of Mn, Si, Al, and Ti, ranging from 0.001 to 0.25%, with some alloying strategies eventually omitting these elements entirely. To monitor the chemical composition, an optical emission spectrometer Q8 Magelan (Bruker-Elemental, Germany) was used, allowing real-time observation of the chemical composition during melting.

As part of the compositional adjustment, trace elements in the raw materials were reduced to increase the metallurgical quality of the molten metal. These measures led to a reduction in dissolved gases (O, N) in the alloy to levels slightly above 10 ppm, as measured by the G8 Galileo gas analyzer (Bruker-Elemental, Germany). Additional refining processes were tested, based on slag with a high Ca content and the passage of inert gas (Ar) through the melt before deoxidation. These processes aimed to improve the metallurgical quality and purity of the alloy.

The chemical composition of the MoNiCr alloys used for additive manufacturing is provided in the following Table 1 Chemical composition of 1-MoNiCr alloy, wt. % Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1 Chemical composition of 1-MoNiCr alloy, wt. %.

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Fe	Mo	Cu	Al	Ti	V	W	Nb	Co	N	O	Ni
0.02	0.25	0.49	0.009	0.012	6.72	2.0	15.7	0.009	0.26	0.04	<0.022	0.082	0.008	0.05	0.0079	0.0062	balance

Table 2 Chemical composition of 2-MoNiCr alloy, wt. %.

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Fe	Mo	Cu	Al	Ti	V	W	Nb	B	N	O	Ni
<0.001	0.19	0.18	<0.003	<0.003	5.8	2.3	16.88	0.002	0.23	0.008	0.019	0.08	0.02	0.001	0.0025	0.0012	balance

The ingots were further processed to achieve a suitable preform for powder atomization. Hot forging of the material was carried out using a hydraulic forging press with a maximum forging force of 2500 tons. This equipment allows for both die and open-die forging. Chamber furnaces without protective atmospheres were used for heating the material. Rolling of the MoNiCr alloy was conducted on a reversing rolling mill, enabling

both hot rolling (two-high roll arrangement) and cold rolling (four-high roll arrangement), with a rolling force of 600 tons and rolling motor torque of 300 kNm. Cold rapid forging was performed using a rapid radial forging machine to produce the final rod preform.

This was followed by ultrasonic atomization. The rod is fed under a plasma column, where the material melts onto the atomization platform. The melt is sprayed through platform oscillation in an inert argon atmosphere (Ar 5N9). The process was conducted under 10 ppm O₂ in the chamber. Comprehensive powder analysis was conducted using a HORIBA LA-960 V2 (HORIBA Ltd., Kyoto, Japan) particle size distribution analyzer, following the ISO 13320 standard. This analysis employed laser scattering to accurately measure particle size and determine particle fraction at specified sizes. The powder's flowability was assessed through testing conducted in compliance with ASTM B213 standards. This test provides a measure of the ease with which the powder flows, a critical parameter in additive manufacturing as it affects layer uniformity and consistency during deposition. Ensuring optimal flowability is essential for achieving high-quality builds and minimizing potential defects caused by irregular powder distribution.

A detailed analysis of the powders used for additive manufacturing and specific printing parameters are described in **Chapter 3**.

2.2. Additive manufacturing

Nickel alloys 1-MoNiCr and 2-MoNiCr were after atomisation additive manufactured. The material blocks were fabricated by DED using a INSSSTEK MX-600 system (InssTek, Daejeon, Korea), which is equipped with a 2- kW yttrium fibre laser, under a protective atmosphere of argon 5.0. The printing parameters are listed in **Table 3** and **Table 4**. The machine uses a 5-axis printing system without supports and with a total building space of 450x600x350 mm. The main advantage of INSSSTEK MX-600 system is the Direct metal tooling (DMT) system used, which monitors the printing process using two cameras and adjusts the laser power during printing to maintain a stable layer thickness. The dimensions of the blocks were 20 × 20 × 20 mm³. Two printing modules SDM800 and SDM 1600 were used by additive manufacturing of 1-MoNiCr alloy while only modul SDM1600 was used by 2-MoNiCr alloy samples fabrication. An example of deposited samples of the 2-MoNiCr alloy, produced using the SDM1600 module, illustrating the general appearance of the alloy post-deposition (**Figure 1**). After additive manufacturing, part of samples 2-MoNiCr alloy were heat treated, specifically by solution annealing in a protective argon atmosphere, with heating to 1200°C, a one-hour hold, and water quenching. The represents the overview of samples prepared as part of the presented experimental program, which were subsequently characterized.

Table 3 Printing parameters for module SDM800

Laser spot size [um]	800
Layer height [um]	250
Hatch distance [um]	500
Powder amount [g/min]	3
Protective gases (coaxial + shield + powder) [l/min]	13
Range of laser power for DMT mode [W]	300-650
Printing strategy	ZigZag CFC+CF

Table 4 Printing parameters for module SDM1600

Laser spot size [um]	1600
Layer height [um]	600
Hatch distance [um]	1100
Powder amount [g/min]	5,6
Protective gases (coaxial + shield + powder) [l/min]	23

Range of laser power for DMT mode [W]	750-1050 and 980-1250
Printing strategy	ZigZag CFC+CF

Figure 1. Deposited samples of 2-MoNiCr alloy.

Table 5 Overview and labeling of additively manufactured (AM) samples

Sample	Processing status
800_1-MoNiCr	AM with module SDM800 of 1-MoNiCr alloy
1600_1-MoNiCr	AM with module SDM1600 of 1-MoNiCr alloy
1600_2-MoNiCr	AM with module SDM1600 of 1-MoNiCr alloy
1600_SA_2-MoNiCr	AM with module SDM1600 and solution annealing of 1-MoNiCr alloy

2.3. Microstructure characterization

The methods and techniques employed for the microstructural characterization of the MoNiCr alloy are outlined, emphasizing their importance in achieving the required mechanical properties. The metallographic samples preparation process included grinding and polishing according to standard procedures, with the final polishing step performed using a 0.25 μm OP-S Non-Dry colloidal silica suspension on a Tegramin 30 (Struers GmbH, Ballerup, Denmark). Observations of the samples' microstructure were made using a Nikon Eclipse MA200 light microscope (LM) (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) supported by NIS Elements 5.2 software for digital imaging and analysis (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan). For more detailed microstructural analysis, a JEOL IT 500 HR scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) equipped with an Octane Elite Super EDS analyzer (EDAX LLC, Mahwah, NJ, USA) was utilized. Data collection, analysis, and post-processing were completed using TEAM 4.5 software (EDAX LLC, Mahwah, NJ, USA).

2.4. Mechanical properties

The local mechanical properties of the material were assessed by testing miniaturized tensile specimens, a widely adopted approach in the additive manufacturing (AM) field, as documented in numerous studies [14,20,21].

The test specimens (Figure 2) were prepared from each block using a wire-electrical-discharge machine (WEDM) and tested in compliance with ISO 6892-1/ASTM E8 standards. The tests were performed on a TiraTest universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell under quasi-static conditions at room temperature, with a strain rate of 0.00025 s^{-1} (A222). The initial dimensions of the specimens were precisely measured using a micrometer, followed by the application of a stochastic black-and-white pattern to enable deformation tracking via an optical system. Given the small specimen size, a non-contact Mercury RT system utilizing digital image correlation (DIC) and a single 2D-calibrated camera was employed to capture deformation during testing. A virtual extensometer with an initial gauge length of 4 mm was used. The recorded force-displacement data provided the basis for evaluating various stress and deformation characteristics, including

yield strength (YS), ultimate tensile strength (UTS), uniform elongation (El), and reduction of area (RA).

Figure 2. Geometry of miniaturized tensile-test specimen.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Additive manufacturing of 1-MoNiCr alloy

3.1.1 Analysis of atomized powder of 1-MoNiCr alloy

The atomized powder of alloy 1-MoNiCr was supplied in the 50-200 μm fraction. Therefore, it was first sieved to the desired fraction of 50-150 μm . The powder was measured using the flowability test according to ASTM B213, yielding a result of 15.7 s. Additionally, the powder's particle size distribution (PSD) was measured on a HORIBA LA-960 device using the dry method. Three measurements were performed in total, with similar results. The PSD measurement results for powder 1-MoNiCr (**Figure 3**) were in the quantiles of $d_{10} = 71 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{50} = 109 \mu\text{m}$, and $d_{90} = 176 \mu\text{m}$. The image shows the alloy particles as approximately spherical, globular particles of various sizes. Some particles exhibit an irregular shape or the presence of smaller attached satellite particles.

Figure 3. Results of PSD measurements on 1-MoNiCr powder and metallography of 1-MoNiCr alloy powder.

3.1.2 Additive manufacturing of the first generation SDM800 module of 1-MoNiCr alloy

The first phase of deposition was carried out on the first-generation SDM800 module. Cubes of 20x20 mm were deposited in various configurations. A constant power was set throughout the printing process at 700W / 350W, with argon cooling, platform preheating to 500°C, and pause optimization of 3.5 s / 10 s between layers or within contour/fill. The

most used mode is DMT, where the printer automatically adjusts the laser power. In this case, an additional idle laser pass was applied, where the laser passes over the printed layer without powder after the layer is completed.

However, in all tested printing variants with the 1-MoNiCr material, many cracks were detected. **Figure 4a** je shows the microstructure of a sample printed in DMT mode.

Figure 4. Microstructures **(a)** 800_1-MoNiCr overview image DMT, **(b)** 1600_1-MoNiCr overview image, **(c)** detailed microstructure with the presence of solidification cracks 800_1-MoNiCr.

In the microstructure of the analyzed samples, solidification cracks were observed (**Figure 4c**), which are characteristic of nickel-based alloys. These cracks were primarily located along grain boundaries and exhibited a dendritic structure, which is typical for this type of defect, occurring during the final stages of solidification. This phenomenon is caused by the uneven distribution of impurities in the last phase of solidification, leading to the localization of residual liquid material at the grain boundaries. During cooling, deformation and stress concentration occur at these boundaries, promoting cavity formation and subsequent crack propagation.

Like other nickel superalloys, these solidification cracks result from a complex interaction of stress and microstructural arrangement during material solidification. The observed cracks are predominantly intergranular, consistent with previously described solidification cracking mechanisms, where the last portions of the melt solidify along grain boundaries, creating weak spots prone to cracking.

This type of cracking confirms the high susceptibility of the alloy to solidification cracking, which is a common phenomenon in nickel alloys, especially during welding or other rapid solidification processes. The observed cracks highlight the need to optimize process parameters and explore additional methods to minimize these defects to ensure adequate material integrity and mechanical resilience in the final product.

Using EDS analysis, elongated particles were observed along grain boundaries in the structure (**Figure 5**), as well as small particles distributed throughout the material. In the upper section of the print, small, nearly equiaxed grains were present. Crack propagation occurred along the boundaries of columnar grains. This material, as manufactured, was unsuitable even for testing mechanical properties.

Figure 5. Results of EDS analysis of first generation sample 800_1-MoNiCr.

3.1.3 Additive manufacturing of the second generation SDM1600 module of 1-MoNiCr alloy

The second phase of the experiment involved using the SDM1600 module for the deposition of the 1-MoNiCr alloy. The optical systems are like those in the first-generation SDM800 module, with differences in the cooling system, powder feed, etc. In this case, two samples were deposited, each in the form of a 20 mm cube. The first sample was deposited using DMT parameters in the range of 750–1050 W, with most of the printing between 900 and 1000 W. The second sample was deposited with a power parameter of 980–1250 W. These two different deposition parameters were chosen based on previous tests and the potential influence of laser power on the result, with the occurrence of cracks being the most important evaluation criterion.

The results exhibited a similar trend to those observed in the first phase of the experiment with the 1-MoNiCr alloy (**Figure 4b**), indicating persistent issues with the formation of solidification cracks. These cracks appeared despite the different laser power parameters and the technical improvements implemented in the SDM1600 module. Although varied laser power settings (750–1050 W for the first sample and 980–1250 W for the second sample) were chosen to potentially influence the solidification process and reduce the likelihood of cracking, the alloy continued to display cohesion issues associated with solidification defects.

Solidification cracks typically arise in the final stages of solidification, where an uneven distribution of solutes along grain boundaries leads to the formation of weak points. These weak zones become susceptible to crack formation due to localized residual stress. The findings indicate that, despite optimized deposition parameters and an improved cooling system in the SDM1600 module, no significant reduction in crack formation was achieved. This suggests that adjusting only the laser power parameters and technical enhancements may be insufficient to fully eliminate problematic solidification defects in the 1-MoNiCr alloy. Consequently, these results highlight the need for further processing adjustments and potential changes in alloy composition to enhance material cohesion and minimize the occurrence of undesirable cracks.

3.1.4 Analysis of impurities in 1-MoNiCr Alloy

Several variants of print parameter settings were tested; however, suitable material free of cracks was not achieved. For this reason, attention was directed toward optimizing the chemical composition of the alloy, as described in **Chapter 2.1**. The goal was to improve material purity, with a particular focus on reducing sulphur, oxygen, and nitrogen content. **Figure 6** shows an intergranular fracture from a tensile test on conventionally produced 1-MoNiCr material, i.e., cast and forged, where sulphur was detected along the grain boundaries (**Figure 7**), which subsequently also contributed to crack formation during additive manufacturing.

Figure 6. Fracture surface of 1-MoNiCr alloy after tensile test.

Figure 7. Results of EDS analysis of 1-MoNiCr alloy.

Detailed analysis revealed that material decohesion occurred due to a combination of two main factors: the presence of sulphur and the occurrence of solidification cracks. Sulphur, known for its detrimental effect on grain boundary cohesion, accumulated along grain boundaries, creating weakened areas. These areas became susceptible to the formation of solidification cracks, which propagated along the grain boundaries and significantly compromised the structural integrity of the material.

As a result, the material produced in this manner was insufficiently cohesive and did not meet the quality standards for further processing. Consequently, it was not suitable for mechanical property testing, as its compromised structure would yield results that were not representative of its performance in practical applications. These findings underscore the importance of controlling impurities and optimizing process parameters to achieve materials with high structural and mechanical stability.

3.2. Additive manufacturing of 2-MoNiCr alloy

As mentioned above, due to the unsuccessful additive manufacturing of the 1-MoNiCr material, the chemical composition of the MoNiCr alloy was optimized to address the identified issues. The results of this study are supported by findings from research of Hu et al. [22] on the effect of sulphur on the embrittlement of nickel alloys, which examined the mechanism of intergranular embrittlement caused by sulphur. By reducing the concentrations of sulphur and other impurities, it is possible to improve the material's purity, leading to enhanced grain cohesion and increased resistance to crack formation. The significance of reducing these elements, as shown in the chemical analysis (Table 2), lies in its positive impact on structural integrity and suitability for additive manufacturing applications.

3.2.1 Analysis of atomized powder of 2-MoNiCr alloy

The conventionally produced material with optimized chemistry, 2-MoNiCr alloy (Table 2), was atomized into powder with a fraction size of 50-125 μm . The powder was tested for flowability according to ASTM B213, resulting in 11.6 s. Additionally, particle size distribution (PSD) was measured on a HORIBA LA-960 device using the dry method. Three measurements were conducted in total, yielding similar results. The PSD measurement results for 2-MoNiCr powder (Figure 8) showed quantiles of $d_{10} = 47 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{50} = 62 \mu\text{m}$, and $d_{90} = 85 \mu\text{m}$. The powder is spherical and free from unwanted satellites.

Figure 8. Results of PSD measurements on 2-MoNiCr powder and metallography of 2-MoNiCr alloy powder.

Overall, the 2-MoNiCr alloy powder demonstrates better flowability and a narrower particle size distribution than the 1-MoNiCr alloy powder. Additionally, the 2-MoNiCr powder is more consistent in particle shape, which may positively impact its properties in the additive manufacturing process, where high flowability and uniform powder distribution are required. The 1-MoNiCr alloy powder has a broader size range and the presence of satellites, which may impair its flowability and uniformity in layer deposition.

Studies [18,19,23] suggest that the characteristics of powder, particularly particle size distribution and shape uniformity, significantly impact flowability and deposition uniformity, which are critical in achieving high-quality printed parts. The 2-MoNiCr alloy powder, which demonstrates better flowability and a narrower PSD, aligns well with findings indicating that more consistent particle shapes and narrower PSDs lead to improved

layer uniformity during the additive manufacturing process [19]. In contrast, the 1-MoNiCr powder, with a broader size range and satellite particles, may experience reduced flowability. The presence of satellites and irregularly shaped particles in 1-MoNiCr could further hinder the deposition quality, reinforcing the importance of optimized powder characteristics for achieving superior mechanical and structural properties in additively manufactured components.

3.2.2 Additive manufacturing of the second generation SDM1600 module of 2-MoNiCr alloy

The optimized 2-MoNiCr alloy was tested exclusively on the SDM1600 device, as this module allows for a higher deposition rate and is better suited to the requirements of industrial applications, thereby enhancing process efficiency and the quality of the final material. Similarly to the deposition of 1-MoNiCr powder, two samples, each in the form of a 20 mm cube, were deposited using the SDM1600 module (**Figure 1**). The first sample was deposited under DMT parameters in the range of 750-1050 W, with most of the printing between 900 and 1000 W. The second sample was deposited with a power parameter of 980-1250 W.

Figure 9. Alloy 1600_2-MoNiCr (a) overview of the sample after additive manufacturing, (b) metallographic analysis of the sample after additive manufacturing, (c) Solidification crack after additive manufacturing.

The microstructure of the additively manufactured material, as shown in images **Figure 9 (a)**, **(b)**, and **(c)**, exhibits several distinctive features. The microstructure reflects the unique characteristics of additive manufacturing, including directional grain growth, layer-by-layer structure, and potential defects such as solidification cracks, which impact the material's mechanical properties. The overview image (**Figure 9a**) shows the layered structure typical of additive manufacturing, with visible layer boundaries resulting from the sequential deposition process. Each layer reflects the deposition path, indicating the formation of melt pools during the process. A closer view (**Figure 9b**) reveals a columnar grain structure aligned along the build direction, which is a common feature in additively manufactured materials. These elongated grains are indicative of the rapid cooling and directional solidification that occurs during the laser-based deposition process. Metallographic analysis revealed that in the additively manufactured samples produced from the optimized 2-MoNiCr alloy powder, only a minimal amount of solidification cracks was observed. **Figure 9c** shows solidification cracks located along grain boundaries, a common defect in nickel-based alloys produced by additive manufacturing. The cracks appear intergranular, likely due to thermal stresses and solute segregation during the final stages of solidification. This feature underscores the need for careful control of processing parameters to minimize cracking and improve structural integrity.

This indicates that the adjustments made to the chemical composition were effective in reducing the formation of these defects, which are typically a challenge in nickel-based

alloys [18]. The optimized composition appears to have improved the solidification process, allowing for a more uniform and defect-resistant microstructure. This reduction in solidification cracking enhances the structural integrity and overall performance of the material, making it better suited for applications requiring high mechanical strength and durability.

In addition to reducing the levels of typical harmful elements (S, O, P), it is also essential to register a reduction in the content of other associated elements such as Al, Ti, Co, Cr, Mn, Cu, Si, as well as C and N. These elements can either directly contribute to the formation of unwanted phases or increase the reactivity of other elements by their presence. The listed elements can form uniformly distributed precipitates—typically $\text{Ni}_3(\text{Al,Ti})$ —or minor phases with preferential occurrences. For example, Ni, Cr, Mo, and Co are elements that commonly form TPC-type (Topological Close-Packed) phases, which can attack grain boundaries with detrimental effects [24,25]. Although the reduction in individual element content may seem relatively minor, the cumulative loss can have a significant impact on the material's properties. MoNiCr is intended as a single-phase material, and the formation of any minor phases is undesirable. Therefore, reducing the levels of these associated elements can contribute to improved technological and functional properties.

3.2.3 Heat Treatment of 2-MoNiCr alloy

To homogenize the material and eliminate traces of the original melt pools formed during the additive manufacturing process, heat treatment was conducted. This involved solution annealing at 1200°C , followed by rapid cooling. The microstructure observed after this heat treatment displayed finer, equiaxed grains with no visible traces of the initial melt pools resulting from the prior additive process. This change in grain structure and the removal of melt pool remnants indicate that the heat treatment was successful in enhancing the uniformity of the microstructure, leading to improved material properties suitable for demanding applications (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10. Metallographic analysis of the sample 1600_SA_2-MoNiCr after additive manufacturing and heat treatment.

3.2.4 Mechanical Properties of 2-MoNiCr alloy

Subsequently, the influence of the microstructure on the resulting mechanical properties was examined. This analysis aimed to understand how the refined, equiaxed grain structure, achieved through heat treatment, affected the material's strength, ductility, and overall performance.

The following **Table 5** and **Figure 11** show the results of the tensile test of the 2-MoNiCr alloy. Properties were measured on the sample both in the as-built condition, directly

after the additive manufacturing process (1600_2-MoNiCr), and after subsequent solution annealing using miniaturized tensile tests-MTT (1600_SA_2-MoNiCr). 509
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Figure 11. Results from tensile tests after additive manufacturing and heat treatment of 2-MoNiCr alloy. 511
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The mechanical property results show differences between the various material states. The highest yield strength (YS) is achieved by the as-built samples (1600_2-MoNiCr) with an average value of 356 ± 7 MPa, accompanied by a moderate scatter in the ultimate tensile strength (UTS), which averages 551 ± 21 MPa. The solution-annealed state (1600_SA_2-MoNiCr) exhibits a slightly lower yield strength, reduced to 279 ± 10 MPa, but with UTS values higher than the as-built state, averaging 602 ± 19 MPa. 514
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The state after additive manufacturing without solution annealing corresponds to a cast structure, where dendrites and associated segregation are still visible. In contrast, the state after additive manufacturing and solution annealing exhibits a recrystallized finer structure typical of an FCC solid solution in nickel alloys, with numerous annealing twins. The higher yield strength observed in the non-annealed printed state could be explained by the presence of strengthening particles of intermediate phases. These phases were eliminated through solution annealing, resulting in a lower yield strength in the annealed state. On the other hand, the annealed state without intermediate phases has a higher potential for work hardening and achieves a higher ultimate tensile strength during tensile testing. 520
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Table 6 Results from tensile tests after additive manufacturing and solution annealing of 2-MoNiCr alloy 531
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Specimen	YS MPa	UTS MPa	EI %	RA %
1600_2-MoNiCr a)	364	581	49.2	75
1600_2-MoNiCr b)	357	541	50.2	67
1600_2-MoNiCr c)	348	532	49.6	73

Average	356±7	551±21	50±0	72±3
1600_SA_2-MoNiCr a)	292	623	54.4	66
1600_SA_2-MoNiCr b)	274	606	52.3	73
1600_SA_2-MoNiCr c)	270	577	47.7	63
Average	279±10	602±19	51±3	67±4

The mechanical properties observed in Hastelloy N alloy [26] exhibits higher tensile strength (approximately 760 MPa) and good yield strength (290 MPa in the base metal and 380 MPa in welded joints). The lower mechanical properties of additively manufactured MoNiCr can be contrasted with conventionally produced Hastelloy N, which was fabricated through conventional manufacturing method, which imparts a "material history" of deformation, resulting in a refined grain structure and that carry through even into the weld metal. These characteristics contribute to Hastelloy N's strength and ductility, as the inherent benefits of the rolling process, i.e. such as grain refinement and work hardening. In contrast, additive manufactured MoNiCr lacks this deformation history.

4. Conclusion

Research successfully demonstrated the potential of the MoNiCr alloy for additive manufacturing in advanced energy applications, particularly through optimizing its chemical composition and processing parameters. The initially tested 1-MoNiCr alloy exhibited issues with solidification cracking, leading to intergranular cracks that weakened the material's structural integrity. By refining the chemical composition to reduce impurities such as sulphur, phosphorus, and oxygen, the development of the 2-MoNiCr alloy achieved a significant decrease in defect formation, resulting in a more cohesive and defect-resistant microstructure.

Mechanical property tests confirmed that the as-built 2-MoNiCr alloy demonstrated a yield strength of 356 ± 7 MPa and an ultimate tensile strength of 551 ± 21 MPa. Post-processing heat treatment further improved its tensile properties, with the solution-annealed samples reaching an ultimate tensile strength of 602 ± 19 MPa, the yield strength slightly decreased to 279 ± 10 MPa.

The development of MoNiCr powder at COMTES FHT, a material not commercially available, underscores the importance of high material purity and consistency in achieving successful additive manufacturing outcomes. Future research will focus on further optimizing the alloy composition and additive manufacturing parameters to enhance the mechanical properties and structural integrity of MoNiCr for demanding energy applications.

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References

1. Muránsky, O.; Yang, C.; Zhu, H.; Karatchevtseva, I.; Sláma, P.; Nový, Z.; Edwards, L. Molten Salt Corrosion of Ni-Mo-Cr Candidate Structural Materials for Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) Systems. *Corros. Sci.* **2019**, *159*, 108087, doi:10.1016/j.corsci.2019.07.011. 577-580
2. Serp, J.; Allibert, M.; Beneš, O.; Delpech, S.; Feynberg, O.; Ghetta, V.; Heuer, D.; Holcomb, D.; Ignatiev, V.; Kloosterman, J.L.; et al. The Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) in Generation IV: Overview and Perspectives. *Prog. Nucl. Energy* **2014**, *77*, 308–319, doi:10.1016/j.pnucene.2014.02.014. 581-583
3. Koukolikova, M.; Slama, P.; Dlouhy, J.; Cerny, J.; Marecek, M. Cold/Hot Deformation Induced Recrystallization of Nickel-Based Superalloys for Molten Salt Reactors. *Metals (Basel)*. **2018**, *8*, doi:10.3390/met8070477. 584-585
4. Reed, R.C.; Rae, C.M.F. *Physical Metallurgy of the Nickel-Based Superalloys*; Fifth Edit.; Elsevier B.V., 2014; Vol. 1; ISBN 9780444537713. 586-587
5. Podany, P.; Novy, Z.; Dlouhy, J. Recrystallization Behaviour of a Nickel-Based Superalloy. *Mater. Tehnol.* **2016**, *50*, 199–205, doi:10.17222/mit.2014.163. 588-589
6. Koukolíková, M.; Sláma, P.; Nový, Z.; Svoboda, P.; Toman, P.; Mareček, M.; Uhlír, J. Research of Materials and Components for Molten Salt Reactors. In Proceedings of the Transactions of the American Nuclear Society; 2017; Vol. 116. 590-591
7. Novy, Z.; Džugan, J.; Wangyao, P.; Kraus, L. Development of Forming Processes for MoNiCr Alloy. *Key Eng. Mater.* **2015**, *658*, 3–7, doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/KEM.658.3. 592-593
8. Novy, Z.; Džugan, J.; Motyčka, P.; Podany, P.; Dlouhy, J. On Formability of MoNiCr Alloy. *Adv. Mater. Res.* **2011**, 295–297, 1731–1737, doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.295-297.1731. 594-595
9. Koukolíková, M.; Simson, T.; Rzepa, S.; Brázda, M.; Džugan, J. The Influence of Laser Power on the Interfaces of Functionally Graded Materials Fabricated by Powder-Based Directed Energy Deposition. *J. Mater. Sci.* **2022**, *57*, 13695–13723, doi:10.1007/s10853-022-07453-9. 596-598
10. Wei, C.; Li, L.; Zhang, X.; Chueh, Y.H. 3D Printing of Multiple Metallic Materials via Modified Selective Laser Melting. *CIRP Ann.* **2018**, *67*, 245–248, doi:10.1016/j.cirp.2018.04.096. 599-600
11. Godec, M.; Malej, S.; Feizpour, D.; Donik, B.; Balažic, M.; Klobčar, D.; Pambaguian, L.; Conradi, M.; Kocijan, A. Hybrid Additive Manufacturing of Inconel 718 for Future Space Applications. *Mater. Charact.* **2021**, *172*, doi:10.1016/j.matchar.2020.110842. 601-602
12. Özel, T.; Shokri, H.; Loizeau, R. A Review on Wire-Fed Directed Energy Deposition Based Metal Additive Manufacturing. *J. Manuf. Mater. Process.* **2023**, *7*, doi:10.3390/jmmp7010045. 603-604
13. Zhou, Y.; Jiang, D.; Al-Akailah, A.; Ning, F. Understanding the Formation of Laser-Induced Melt Pools with Both Wire and Powder Feeding in Directed Energy Deposition. *Addit. Manuf.* **2024**, *89*, 104312, doi:10.1016/j.addma.2024.104312. 605-606
14. Melzer, D.; Džugan, J.; Koukolíková, M.; Rzepa, S.; Vavřík, J. Structural Integrity and Mechanical Properties of the Functionally Graded Material Based on 316L/IN718 Processed by DED Technology. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* **2021**, *811*, doi:10.1016/j.msea.2021.141038. 607-609
15. Qiu, C.; Chen, H.; Liu, Q.; Yue, S.; Wang, H. On the Solidification Behaviour and Cracking Origin of a Nickel-Based Superalloy during Selective Laser Melting. *Mater. Charact.* **2019**, *148*, 330–344, doi:10.1016/j.matchar.2018.12.032. 610-611
16. Zhao, Y.; Ma, Z.; Yu, L.; Liu, Y. New Alloy Design Approach to Inhibiting Hot Cracking in Laser Additive Manufactured Nickel-Based Superalloys. *Acta Mater.* **2023**, *247*, 118736, doi:10.1016/j.actamat.2023.118736. 612-613
17. Mathias, L.E.T.; Pinotti, V.E.; Batistão, B.F.; Rojas-Arias, N.; Figueira, G.; Andreoli, A.F.; Gargarella, P. Metal Powder as Feedstock for Laser-Based Additive Manufacturing: From Production to Powder Modification. *J. Mater. Res.* **2024**, *39*, 19–47, doi:10.1557/s43578-023-01271-8. 614-616
18. Brennan, M.C.; Keist, J.S.; Palmer, T.A. Defects in Metal Additive Manufacturing Processes. *J. Mater. Eng. Perform.* **2021**, *30*, 4808–4818, doi:10.1007/s11665-021-05919-6. 617-618
19. Chandra, S.; Wang, C.; Tor, S.B.; Ramamurty, U.; Tan, X. Powder-Size Driven Facile Microstructure Control in Powder-Fusion 619

- Metal Additive Manufacturing Processes. *Nat. Commun.* **2024**, *15*, 1–14, doi:10.1038/s41467-024-47257-w. 620
20. Melzer, D.; Džugan, J.; Koukolíková, M.; Rzepa, S.; Dlouhý, J.; Brázda, M.; Bucki, T. Fracture Characterisation of Vertically 621
Build Functionally Graded 316L Stainless Steel with Inconel 718 Deposited by Directed Energy Deposition Process. *Virtual* 622
Phys. Prototyp. **2022**, *17*, 821–840, doi:10.1080/17452759.2022.2073793. 623
21. Pehlivan, E.; Roudnicka, M.; Džugan, J.; Koukolikova, M.; Králík, V.; Seifi, M.; Lewandowski, J.J.; Dalibor, D.; Daniel, M. 624
Effects of Build Orientation and Sample Geometry on the Mechanical Response of Miniature CP-Ti Grade 2 Strut Samples 625
Manufactured by Laser Powder Bed Fusion. *Addit. Manuf.* **2020**, *35*, doi:10.1016/j.addma.2020.101403. 626
22. Hu, T.; Yang, S.; Zhou, N.; Zhang, Y.; Luo, J. Role of Disordered Bipolar Complexions on the Sulfur Embrittlement of Nickel 627
General Grain Boundaries. *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, *9*, doi:10.1038/s41467-018-05070-2. 628
23. Kennedy, S.K.; Dalley, A.M.; Kotyk, G.J. Additive Manufacturing: Assessing Metal Powder Quality Through Characterizing 629
Feedstock and Contaminants. *J. Mater. Eng. Perform.* **2019**, *28*, 728–740, doi:10.1007/s11665-018-3841-5. 630
24. Belan, J. GCP and TCP Phases Presented in Nickel-Base Superalloys. *Mater. Today Proc.* **2016**, *3*, 936–941, 631
doi:10.1016/j.matpr.2016.03.024. 632
25. Long, F.; Yoo, Y.S.; Jo, C.Y.; Seo, S.M.; Jeong, H.W.; Song, Y.S.; Jin, T.; Hu, Z.Q. Phase Transformation of η and σ Phases in an 633
Experimental Nickel-Based Superalloy. *J. Alloys Compd.* **2009**, *478*, 181–187, doi:10.1016/j.jallcom.2008.11.121. 634
26. Wang, S.; Ma, B.; Feng, D.; Chen, S.; Ma, Y.; Li, H.; Lv, C.; Zheng, W.; Yang, J. Microstructure, Mechanical Properties and 635
Fatigue Crack Growth Behavior of Gas Tungsten Arc Welding Welded Joint of the Hastelloy N Alloy. *Materials (Basel)*. **2023**, 636
16, doi:10.3390/ma16196510. 637
638